

WASTE TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES

Salixova Ozoda Abdullayeva

candidate of technical sciences, associate professor of the

Tashkent institute of chemical technology

E-mail: ozodaxon.salihova@gmail.com

Sidikova Gulchekhra Abdualolovna

Senior Lecturer, Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

E-mail: gulihonsidikova@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7805350>

For oil companies, the great problem is to ensure an efficient environmental protection, avoiding over costs that might affect competitiveness. Therefore, the search for effective solutions at lower cost has a promising future. Currently, the treatment of waste from pits includes i) physical and chemical processes (removal of free phase, thermal desorption, excavation and disposal in landfill, deep injection in the wells, dehydration, incineration, neutralization, solidification and stabilization) and ii) biological processes (landfarming, biopiles, composting, phytoremediation and bioreactor).

Thermal techniques contribute significantly to the presence of heavy metals in aerosols. It is thus important to ascertain the quantities and chemical forms of the heavy metals that are emitted because their behavior strongly depends on the thermal and chemical environments.

Solidification/ stabilization is currently applied on some mud pits and seems to be very effective. However, the use of solidification consists of a pollution transfer and/or containment without removing or even reducing the concentration of the initial soil pollution. Thus, solidification ensures the confinement of heavy metals and hydrocarbons and leaching, a simulation of rain wash, does not allow pollutant desorption. Losses can be due to a combination of factors including biodegradation, abiotic degradation, volatilization and migration.

Biological treatments offer a suitable combination between economical issues and environmental protection. This should help operators to reduce drilling costs, while simultaneously increasing production and enhancing environment-oriented efforts. With a high potential for destroying environmental pollutants, bioremediation of crude oil-polluted soils (by degradation and detoxification) is becoming an increasingly important remedial option. The use of inexpensive equipment, the environmentally-friendly nature and simplicity of the process are some of its advantages over remedial alternatives such as physical and chemical treatments.

Numerous methods used for managing drilling wastes have been described in detail in the Drilling Waste Management Information System website . They mainly include:

- waste minimization, which reduces volumes or impacts of wastes by minimizing the generation of drilling wastes thanks to special drilling techniques (*e.g.* directional drilling, smaller diameter holes, use of lower amount of fluid) or by using muds and additives with lower environmental impacts (*e.g.* SOBM or new drilling fluid systems or alternate weighting agents),
- recycle/reuse, *e.g.* mud recycle, roadspreading, reuse of cuttings for construction purposes, restoration of wetlands using cuttings or even use of oily cuttings as fuel,
- other miscellaneous managing drilling waste methods like disposal through onsite burial (pits, landfills), land application (landfarming, landspreading), bioremediation (composting, bioreactors, vermiculture), discharge to ocean, offsite disposal to commercial facilities, slurry injection, salt caverns or thermal treatments (incineration, thermal desorption). A combination of bioremediation with phytoremediation can afford better results for heavy metals. The selection of the treatment and the remediation technology of contaminated soils in the oil industry are then highly dependent on the drilling fluid composition but also on the environment regulations of the countries, geographic conditions, hydrogeology and climate of the drilled sites. Figure.1 shows drilling fluid waste sources and management methodology.

Fig. 1. Drilling fluid waste sources and management methodology Life Cycle Assessment of drilling fluid. Using Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach, recent work of Ghazi et al., evaluates the life cycle of all drilling muds, and compares four scenarios of treatment and disposal: thermal desorption, on-line and off-

line stabilization/solidification and abandonment of reserve pit (without treatment). The preliminary results obtained show that LCA is a **Health effects**. Some adverse health effects associated with drilling muds are i) irritation of the skin, eyes or alimentary mucosa caused by either low pH mud, surfactant or nuisance dust (de- aromatized hydrocarbons can enhance irritancy), ii) secondary irritation when prolonged and repeated contact (base oils/solvents) with skin will remove natural fats and oils to cause redness, drying and cracking, iii) respiratory irritation primarily from nuisance dusts, iv) inhalation effects such as acute central nervous system (CNS) depression when working with hydrocarbon solvents, especially at elevated temperatures. Solvents used in OBM are of low vapor pressure, and thus should not cause problems of CNS depression, although nausea and headache can occur, v) possible sensitization to biocides and finally vi) possible carcinogenicity due to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and asbestos.

Particle size as a source of benefit and damage. In dispersion tests, our recommendation is to use, preferably, small size cuttings, which are in close contact with all additives used in drilling fluid systems. Moreover, when clays are fully exposed to the fluid, the aggregation effect is eliminated.

However, invasion of fine particles issued from drilling fluids (bentonite, barite, calcite,) also called 'mud invasion', or from geological sediments present in the formation, blocks the pores or at least narrows them down. This causes a decrease in the permeability of the formation thereby leading to a decrease in production rate. The economic consequences of this damage justify a thorough study of this problem in order to find ways to minimize its effects.

It has also been shown experimentally that WBM impair the formation permeability more significantly than OBM and polymer-based muds. The filtrate generated by WBM is more likely to cause physical interactions and chemical reactions with in situ reservoir fluid and rock, inducing severe damage.

Heavier OBM used to drill reservoir sections especially in undeveloped sectors where reservoir pressure is believed to be still high also leads to the main formation damage. This may be due to the particle invasion of the organophilic clays used as viscosifiers.

References:

1. Aadnoy, B.S. (2003). Introduction to special issue on Borehole Stability, J. Petr. Sci. Eng., 38, 79-82.
2. Laboratory Testing of Drilling Fluids, Seventh Edition and ISO 10416: 2002 API 13I Supplement 2 - 01-June.

3. Audibert, A. and Dalmazzone, C. (2006). Surfactant system for water-based well fluids. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physico-chem. Eng. Aspects*, 288, 113-120.
4. Benna, M.; Kbir-Ariguib, N.; Clinard, C. and Bergaya, F. (2001). Static filtration of purified sodium bentonite clay suspensions. Effect of clay content. *Applied Clay Sci.*, 19, 103-120.
5. Coussot, P.; Bertrand, F. and Herzhaft, B. (2004). Rheological Behavior of Drilling Muds, Characterization Using MRI Visualization. *Oil & Gas Sci. Technol. - Rev. IFP*, 59(1,) 23-29.
6. Dalmazzone, C.; Audibert-Hayett, A.; Quintero, L.; Jones, T.; Dewatinnes, C. and Jansen, M. (2006). Optimizing filtrate design to minimize in-situ and wellbore damage to water-wet reservoirs during drill-in. *SPE Prod.* 66-73, Feb.
7. Greaves, C.; Rojas, J.C. and Chambers, B. (2001). Field Application of "Total Fluid Management" of Drilling Fluids and Associated Wastes, paper SPE 66552 presented at the SPE/EPA/DOE Exploration and Production Environmental Conference, San Antonio, Texas, 26-28 February

